

THE FORMS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION THAT ARE PREFERRED BY PUPILS OF DIFFERENT DEMOGRAPHIC AND MEDICAL GROUPS, BY TEACHERS AND PARENTS

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Abstract

*There are no studies based on a comparative analysis of the responses of parents, their children and teachers of physical culture. The locality of complete and accurate information makes the right choice of the means and forms of physical education of pupils rather complicated. **Aim of research** – to identify the forms of physical education, which are popular among students and are appropriate according to the opinion of parents and physical culture teachers. Over 150 works of native scientists have been processed. A questionnaire of 182 physical culture teachers from 102 secondary schools in the Ukraine; 1017 pupils of middle school age and their parents has been conducted. We have used nonparametric methods. The forms of sports-oriented physical education are significantly ahead of short physical exercising and motile breaks by popularity. In the rating of parents, short physical exercise leads, and the results in this group are only slightly inferior to advocating sports sections. Teachers of physical culture also pay great attention to sports sections, sports competitions and short physical exercise. The results for pupils of the special medical group are definitely more interesting than for other children. The decline of interest in "aging" pupils is observed within all forms of physical education, but the highest reduction of interest is in the attitude of pupils to "little" forms. Sports sections, sports competitions, short physical exercise and motile breaks are the favorites among middle school age pupils. Although participation in sports competitions and advocating sports sections are more preferred by boys than girls.*

Key words: Physical education, pupils, teachers, parents

Introduction

During extremely limited duration of the lesson one cannot fully solve sanative tasks of physical education in schools, thus an essential factor of the pupils' health preservation and prevention of their refer to special medical groups for physical education classes is sports and recreational activities in the pupil's daily routine.

Extra-curricular work in physical education must contribute to solving a number of important interconnected tasks, such as: health promotion, hardening, increase of pupils' efficacy, the development and correction of physical and motor abilities of pupils, improvement of vital motor skills and abilities, their application in different terms, forming healthy lifestyle habits, positive attitude towards physical education, motivation and goals of the active motor activity, promoting learning of required minimum of

knowledge in the field of hygiene, medicine, physical culture and sports; improvement of psycho-emotional state, moral and volitional qualities and aesthetic education; answer the communication needs of pupils, bringing up a need in regular physical exercise, striving for physical perfection, willingness to work and protect the interests of the motherland. Underestimation of the importance of extracurricular forms of physical education in present-day conditions leads to an increase in school diseases, including visual, posture and neuropsychiatric abnormalities.

A very important condition of the effectiveness of extracurricular activities in physical education is a choice of physical exercise forms, which would meet the interests of the pupils and had great sanative effect. **Analysis of recent research and publications** proves unduly low interest of researchers to the

problem. Virtually there is no data on the attitude peculiarities of children referred to various medical groups. There are no studies based on comparative analysis of the responses of parents, their children and teachers of physical culture. Locality of complete and accurate information makes the right choice of means and forms of physical education of pupils rather complicated.

Aim of research – to identify the forms of physical education which are popular among students and are appropriate according to the opinion of parents and physical culture teachers.

Research tasks:

1. To identify forms of physical education, which are popular among students of different demographic, sexual and medical groups;
2. To identify forms of physical education, which are more preferred by physical culture teachers;
3. To find out what forms of physical education are considered optimal from the point of view of the parents;
4. To compare ratings of the significance of physical education forms made by pupils, parents and teachers of physical culture.

Material and Methods. We used methods of analysis and synthesis of empirical data and literary data. In particular, over 150 works of native scientists have been processed.

A survey (questionnaire) of physical culture teachers in four regions of Ukraine has been conducted. We polled 182 respondents from 102 secondary schools located in urban and rural areas.

A total of 1017 pupils of middle school age of rural and urban secondary schools in four regions of Ukraine, including 510 girls and 507 boys has been polled. There were 365 pupils – representatives of 5th grade, 7th grade – 342 pupils, 9th grade – 310 pupils. The sample included 671 pupils referred by doctors to basic, 327 pupils – to preparatory and 59 pupils – to special medical group (SMG). Among the parents who participated in the survey there were 13,58% of men and 86,42% – of women.

For processing of the data we have applied methods of mathematical statistics. To confirm the hypothesis about the reliability of the differences between the two averages we have used nonparametric methods.

Results. Discussion. We have found that among all forms of physical education (Fig. 1) pupils of secondary school age are the most interested in participating in sports clubs (41.9%). Every sixth pupil (37.6%) likes to participate in sports competitions directly. Significant advantage of these organizational forms, among others confirms the benefits of sports-oriented (sportized) physical education.

Fig. 1. Organizational forms of physical education preferred by middle school age pupils.

The value of competitions – the main attribute of sports in physical education of pupils can't be overestimated. Competitions are a good school of life, a means of personality formation. Application of competitions in academic and extracurricular activities offers great opportunities for increase of activity and improvement of pupils' emotional state. It is a well-known fact that specific competitive relations tend to reveal marginal physical and mental capabilities of every pupil up to the extreme mobilization of functional reserves of the body and thus stimulate their development. Due to this different variants of competitive forms are quite common not only in the sports movement, but in most areas of physical culture practice. In physical education competitive forms of classes are not as much a way to achieve significant sporting and technical result or sporting victory, but as a form of emotional content of communication, healthy recreation and entertainment.

Taking part in the competitions, especially with parents, pupils enrich themselves with new impressions, get to know themselves and their friends more closely, with parents experiencing the joy of victory and the bitterness of defeat. The atmosphere of competitions enables to realize the importance of physical exercise. Therefore, it is worth to apply in physical education lessons more elements of competitions and conduct the lessons with priority use of certain kinds of sport.

Other forms of physical education are significantly lacking behind ($p < 0.0000$) in the popularity from the two abovementioned. Second in the list of the most popular forms of physical education are short physical exercising, motile breaks, gymnastics before classes as well as – days of health and theoretical lessons of physical culture. Obviously, pupils feel physiological need to use exercise to relax after intellectual load and to rest by means of physical education. Performing elementary exercise during lessons (short physical exercising or middle physical exercising) and active games during breaks between lessons (while motile breaks) can significantly enhance mental performance of pupils, prevent its decline at the end of the school day, resist the appearance of scoliosis or kyphosis and poor eyesight, improve emotional

state of pupils. However, in present-day schools "small" forms of physical education are practically neglected, especially – in the middle and high school [1, 2, 3, 4]. Pupils also do not perform exercises complexes of short physical exercising at home: 28% of teens do not exercise at all, and 53% of the pupils go on a break to rest only when fatigue comes, in an effort to do homework more quickly. While doing homework middle physical exercising are regularly performed only by 8% of teens and irregularly by – 11% respectively [12]. Other forms of physical education scored less than 12 percent, meaning that they became the third most popular group.

Analysis of our data showed that parents consider short physical exercising an optimal form of physical education in schools (Fig. 2). This organizational form substantially (by 4.6%) is ahead of the next in the list of parents.

Going in for sports sections are also important, according to a large part of the parents (42.4%), about the same number as among children (41.9%). Sports classes are the most appropriate to organize for well-trained children, while classes in therapeutic physical culture should be conducted for children with health deviations (39.9%), according to the parents' opinion.

The significance of dance classes (35.8%) and mobile interruptions (35.8%), and days of health and physical culture (35.2%) indicates that they constitute the fourth group in the parents' list of the most popular organizational forms of physical education.

Children's participation in sports competitions, according to 31.2% of parents is not as effective (7th place in the list), but according to their children (37.6% and 2nd place in the rating). Mass recreational activities, gymnastics before lessons, middle physical exercising, theoretical lessons of physical culture, non-traditional forms of physical education and tutoring of pupils in extracurricular time (27.1% -11.2%) are productive in the opinion of each 4-10th parent, i.e. have minor impact on pupils and, therefore, require modifications. Homework in physical education is considered an effective form of physical education by a quite small number of parents

(6.5%). Therefore, when using this form, one should also make adjustments.

Fig. 2. Organizational forms of physical education, advisable in schools according to parents' opinion of middle school age pupils.

One should take into account the tendency in the rating of children and their parents. In the responses of children it had exponential form. This indicates a sharp decrease in the importance of forms since the second position. Parents, on the contrary, – showed an abrupt decline in the forms placed in the second half of the list.

We observe a slightly different succession of physical education forms in the list of teachers compared to the previous two. In particular, the tendency shows that physical culture teachers give much more importance to each of the abovementioned forms than parents and children

do (Fig. 3). It is obvious that parents and children underestimate the value of most of them (except for dance classes and gymnastics before lessons), probably, because of the lack of awareness on these issues. As the figure shows, theoretical lessons of physical culture are not considered by parents and their children as an effective form of physical education. Therefore, it will be useful to improve the system of formation of theoretical training of pupils as they are prospective parents as well. It will be worthy to examine the dependence of their attitude towards physical education depending on their age and level of education.

Fig. 3. Organizational forms of physical education

All the respondents in improvement of school children's health pay great attention to involvement in sports sections (Table 1).

Therefore, this form is substantially ahead of the next form in the list.

Table 1. Organizational forms of physical education, advisable in schools

General place in the rating	Organizational forms of physical education	parents	pupils	teachers
1	Going in for sports sections	2	1	1
2	Short physical exercising	1	4	2-3
3-4	Sports competitions	7	2	4
3-4	Motile break	4	3	6
5	Days of health and physical culture	6	5	2-3
6	Mass recreational activities	8	8	5
7	Classes in therapeutic physical culture	3	11	7-8
8	Dance classes	5	9	13-14
9	Gymnastics before lessons	9	6	12
10-11	Middle physical exercising	10	10	7-8
10-11	Theoretical lessons of physical culture	11	7	10
12	Homework in physical culture	14	12	9
13	Tutoring of pupils in extracurricular time	13	13	11
14	New, non-traditional forms of physical education	12	14	13-14

Short physical exercising were rated at highest by parents, teachers assigned them 2-3 places, children put them on the 4th place. As a result, this form is second in importance.

Teachers of physical culture give greater significance to mass recreational activities (5th place in the rating against 8th), short physical exercising (7-8th against 10th) and homework in physical culture than given by parents and children (9th position against the 14th and 12th respectively). Parents and children have higher

rating in motile breaks (4th and 3rd place to 6th in the list of teachers). As a result of data processing, motile breaks share the 3rd and 4th places with sports competitions, are one of the three priority forms of physical activity at school.

In the course of the research it was discovered that there is a dependence between the value of a particular form of physical education and the level of pupils' health (Figure 4).

1 – theoretical lessons of physical culture, 2 – classes in therapeutic physical culture, 3 – tutoring of pupils in extracurricular time, 4 – gymnastics before lessons, 5 – short physical exercising, 6 – middle physical exercising, 7 – motile breaks, 8 – homework in physical culture, 9 – going in for sports sections, 10 – sports competitions, 11 – mass recreational activities, 12 – days of health and physical culture, 13 – new, non-traditional forms of physical education

Fig. 4. Forms of physical education, which pupils of various medical groups are interested in.

Pupils of Special Medical Group (SMG) are clearly ($p < 0.05$) more interested in theoretical physical culture lessons than others, they like to do exercises of short physical exercising ($p > 0.05$), and especially those of middle physical exercising ($p < 0.05$), as well as to do homework in physical culture ($p < 0.05$ – compared to the pupils of basic medical group). Unimportant, unlike the rest, the pupils of SMG find gymnastics before lessons and days of health ($p > 0.05$). However, the most interesting among physical forms in school, just like all other pupils, the pupils of SMG find going in for the sports sections and sports competitions; second the most important among children's priorities are short physical exercising and motile breaks. We

have found that with age, the succession of physical education forms, which are popular with children is changing as well (Fig. 5). Most of the organizational forms of physical education lose popularity the senior children are, but the largest and most significant decline is observed in the interest of pupils to short physical exercising ($p < 0.000$), motile breaks ($p < 0.001$) and middle physical exercising ($p < 0.01$) and gymnastics before lessons ($p < 0.01$). Theoretical lessons lose their value in the 9th form ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, it is in the methodology and the organization of these forms of physical education significant changes should be made in order to maintain the interest of pupils throughout the entire period of studying at the school.

1 – theoretical lessons of physical culture, 2 – classes in therapeutic physical culture, 3 – tutoring of pupils in extracurricular time, 4 – gymnastics before lessons, 5 – short physical exercising, 6 – middle physical exercising, 7 – motile breaks, 8 – homework in physical culture, 9 – going in for sports sections, 10 – sports competitions, 11 – mass recreational activities, 12 – days of health and physical culture, 13 – new, non-traditional forms of physical education

Fig. 5. Forms of physical education, which pupils of various age groups are interested in.

The obtained data allow us to conclude that there are almost no gender differences in the popularity of various forms of physical education among pupils of secondary school age (Fig. 6). The only exceptions are gymnastics before lessons that is more attractive to girls than boys ($p < 0.000$) and sports competitions, which are more appreciated by boys ($p < 0.001$). Gender differences viewing interest in sports sections were close to credible ($P = 0.07$), but were not confirmed statistically.

Conclusions. Among the pupils of middle school age, forms of sports-oriented physical education (going in for sports sections and taking part in sports competitions) are significantly ($p < 0.0000$) ahead of short physical exercising and motile breaks by popularity. In the rating of parents, short physical exercising are leading, they are only slightly ($p > 0.05$) inferior to going in for sports sections. Children's participation in sports competitions, according to parents' opinion (31.2%) is not as effective (7th place in

the rating) as believed by their children (37.6% and 2nd place). Teachers of physical culture also pay great attention to going in for sports sections (92.0%), sports competitions (77.0%) and short physical exercising (78.0%).

The dependence between the importance of certain forms of physical education and level of pupils' health has been defined. For pupils of special medical group definitely ($p < 0.05$) more interesting than for other children, are theoretical lessons of physical culture; children with health

deviations prefer to do exercises of short physical exercising ($p > 0.05$) and middle physical exercising ($p < 0.05$) as well as do homework in physical culture on their own ($p < 0.05$ - with indicators of practically healthy pupils). The choice of these forms of special medical group pupils can be explained by relatively lower efficiency level and possibly by mental characteristics inherent to them.

1 – theoretical lessons of physical culture, 2 – classes in therapeutic physical culture, 3 – tutoring of pupils in extracurricular time, 4 – gymnastics before lessons, 5 – short physical exercising, 6 – middle physical exercising, 7 – motile breaks, 8 – homework in physical culture, 9 – going in for sports sections, 10 – sports competitions, 11 – mass recreational activities, 12 – days of health and physical culture, 13 – new, non-traditional forms of physical education

Fig. 6. Forms of physical education, which pupils of different gender are interested in.

The decline of interest of "aging" pupils is observed within all forms of physical education, but the highest reduction of interest is in the attitude of pupils to "little" forms ($p < 0,000-0,01$).

Going in for sports sections, sports competitions, short physical exercising and motile breaks are the favorites among middle school age pupils, even those referred to special

medical groups. Even when growing up, the pupils do not lose interest to these forms of physical education, but on the contrary ÷ the interest to sports competitions is only growing. Although participation in sports competitions ($p < 0.000$) and going in for sports sections ($p = 0.07$) are more preferred by boys than girls.

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